

BELOWGROUND PLANT LIFE: FEASIBILITY STUDY ON THE USE OF ROOT TRAITS TO EXPLAIN TIME CHANGES IN VEGETATION AT THE VELINO-DUCHESSA LTER SITE

Petriccione B.¹, Gregg S.²

¹Carabinieri, Forest and Environmental Protection Dpt.; ²Citizen scientist

Presenting author: Bruno Petriccione, b.petriccione@gmail.com

Changes in vegetation have been recorded over the last 30 years in the high-mountain plant communities of the Monte di Sevice research station, belonging to the “Appennino Centrale: Velino-Duchessa” LTER site (<https://deims.org/12c79ecb-7890-4b75-9655-0883dacd8a29>). Systematic sampling was carried out in two high-mountain plant communities, alpine tundra (*Saxifraga speciosae-Silenetum ceniasiae*) and snow-bed grassland (*Trifolium thalii-Festucetum microphyllae*), ranging from 2100-2200 m a.s.l.. Preliminary results on the recorded time changes were published in 2005 (1) and 2021 (2), based on species occurrence and their relative coverage, life forms and strategies. While aboveground plant functional traits have been sufficiently investigated, the belowground plant life has remained almost completely unexplored until now. On the basis of 30 years of ecological research (phytosociological relevés systemically collected in 18 years, from 1993 to 2022, and microclimate measurements recorded in the same site over 10 years, starting in 2014), a feasibility study has been carried out to interpret time changes through the root traits of the most sensitive and locally invasive species. The hypothesis is that the belowground component of the biocenosis is even more negatively affected by the increased frequency and duration of frost periods, connected to the increased discontinuity of snow coverage in winter.

- 1) Petriccione B., 2005. Short-term changes in key plant communities of Central Apennines (Italy). *Acta Botanica Gallica*, 152: 545-561 (<https://doi.org/10.1080/12538078.2005.10515513>).
- 2) Cutini M., Theurillat J.-P., Petriccione B. et al., 2021. Appennino Centrale: Velino-Duchessa, p. 74-79. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5584729>). In: Capotondi L., Ravaioli M., Acosta A., Chiarini F., Lami A., Stanisci A., Tarozzi L., Mazzocchi M.G. (a cura di). *La Rete Italiana per la Ricerca Ecologica di Lungo Termine. Lo studio della biodiversità e dei cambiamenti*, pp. 806.